

The US National Gemini Office at NSF's NOIRLab

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The US National Gemini Office (US NGO) is a group within the Community Science and Data Center (CSDC) at NSF's NOIRLab. The goal of the US NGO is to support US Gemini users in all phases of the astronomical observing cycle, from proposal preparation to data analysis.

The US NGO recently published an article on its history and services in SPIE's *Journal of Astronomical Telescopes, Instruments, and Systems (JATIS)* [1]. The article provides a brief historical overview of the US NGO through its almost 30 years of existence and its evolving role within the International Gemini Observatory partnership, NOAO, and, more recently, NOIRLab. The article provides a thorough discussion of the efforts and products currently being developed by the US NGO staff and how those help increase engagement with the user community in the US and with the other Gemini partners. These efforts and products include

data reduction cookbooks, helpdesk support, and engagement through social media, among others. In addition, the article describes how the US NGO quantifies user engagement and outreach through website analytics and metrics, which help focus the effort allocation and distribution within the team. An example of these analytics is given in the figure, showing the number of unique visitors to the GMOS Data Reduction Cookbook in a 18-month period.

References

- [1] Placco, V. & Stanghellini, L. 2023, *JATIS* 9(1), 017003. [doi:10.1117/1.JATIS.9.17003](https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JATIS.9.17003), [10.48550/arXiv.2304.10657](https://arxiv.org/abs/10.48550/arXiv.2304.10657), [ADS 2023JATIS...9a7003P](#)
[US NGO website](#)
[GMOS Data Reduction Cookbook](#)
[US NGO on Twitter](#)

